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COMPARING THE CHEMICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BERMET AND ITS BASE WINE

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Bermet is a unique aromatic dessert wine from Sremski Karlovci, a well-known winemaking area on Fruška Gora mountain in northern Serbia, which was originally created for medicinal purposes. This wine is made by adding various herbs and spices to the base wine to enhance the maceration of aromatic compounds. While mugwort is the main ingredient in every Bermet, each winery adds its own secret mix of herbs and spices. The aim of this study was to investigate how added herbs and spices influence the chemical composition and biological activity of the base wines and to identify the features they contribute to Bermet wine. For this purpose, 2 white, 1 rosé and 5 red base wines were compared with their respective Bermet wines. The polyphenolic profile was determined with LC-MS/MS and HPLC-UV/VIS methods, while total soluble solids (TSS) were measured with a refractometer. Spectrophotometric methods were used to assess the antioxidant activity by measuring how well the samples scavenge HO[•], and to evaluate their neuroprotective properties by testing their ability to inhibit the enzyme acetylcholinesterase. From 75 analysed polyphenols, 50 were quantified in examined samples. Bermet wines contained polyphenols that are not characteristic for base wines, however base wines had greater amounts of main polyphenolics, such as anthocyanins, flavan-3-ols and gallic acid. TSS were higher in all Bermet wines, probably due to a higher sugar content. All base wines expressed significantly higher neuroprotective activity, while the antioxidant activity was similar between base and respective Bermet wines. This study highlighted the chemical changes that occur during the making of Bermet and how those changes affect the evaluated biological activities. Each Bermet gained unique characteristics from the added herbs and spices, although the biological potential of base wines has lowered during Bermet production process.

Keywords: Bermet, wine, polyphenols, sugar, antioxidants, acetylcholinesterase

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